

Supporting Information

V-Shaped Träger Oligothiophenes Boost Triplets Formation by CT mediation and Symmetry Breaking

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1. Synthesis and Characterization

All the chemicals were purchased from commercial suppliers and used without further purification. Compounds **3**,¹ **4**,² **TB**³ and **TB-CHO**³ were obtained as previously described or with some modifications. The thiophene-based analogue **DCVT2** was synthesized according to the literature.² ¹H-NMR and ¹³C-NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Avance 300 MHz spectrometer. Chemical shifts are reported in ppm and referenced to the residual non-deuterated solvent frequencies (CDCl₃: δ 7.26 ppm for ¹H, δ 77.0 ppm for ¹³C, Acetone-*d*₆: δ 2.05 ppm for ¹H, δ 29.8 and 206 ppm for ¹³C, DMSO-*d*₆: δ 2.50 ppm for ¹H, and 39.5 ppm for ¹³C).

Scheme S1. Synthetic route described in the article for the Tröger base analogues **TB1**, **TB2** and **TB3** and the model compound **DCVT2**.

(4*R*,9*R*)-5,10-dihydro-4,9-methanodithieno[3,2-*b*:3',2'-*f*][1,5]diazocine – **TB**

Under Ar atmosphere, **1** (1g, 5,4 mmol) is suspended in 10 mL of dry dichloromethane. The mixture is cooled to 0 °C and 7,5 mL of TFA is added, as it is described previously.⁴ The reaction is stirred 1h at room temperature and then the solvent is removed under reduced pressure. The obtained crude is dissolved in 6 mL of MeOH and 2,22 mL of HCl (37%) and 2,53 mL of CH₂O are added to the reaction. The mixture is stirred at 27 °C overnight and once the time is complete the crude is poured into aqueous ammonia solution (4%) and extracted with dichloromethane. The combined organic phases were washed with brine and dried over MgSO₄. After removal the solvent, the crude was washed several times with cold methanol to obtain the pure product **TB** as a white solid (31%).

¹H-NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃): δ (ppm) = 7.11 (d, 5.3 Hz, 1H), 6.83 (d, J = 5.3 Hz, 1H), 4.58 (d, J = 16 Hz, 1H), 4.23 (s, 1H), 4.13 (d, J = 16 Hz, 1H).

¹³C-NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃): δ (ppm) = 144.86, 123.24, 123.10, 122.98, 68.00, 53.68.

(4*R*,9*R*)-2,7-bis(trimethylstannyl)-5,10-dihydro-4,9-methanodithieno[3,2-*b*:3',2'-*f*][1,5]diazocine – **TB-Sn**

To a solution of **TB** (100 mg, 0.43 mmol) in 6 mL of dry THF at 0 °C a solution of *n*-BuLi (0.8 mL, 1.6 M in hexane) was added and the mixture was stirred 30 min. at room temperature and then cooled to -78 °C. To the cooled solution ClSnMe₃ (255mg, 1.5 eq., in 2 mL of dry THF) was added and the solution was warmed up to room temperature slowly and stirred for 30 min. at room temperature. Then, water was added to the reaction, extracted with dichloromethane (x3) and the

organic phases were washed with brine and dried over MgSO₄. After removal of the solvent, the organic oily residue was used without further purification.

¹H-NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃): δ (ppm) = 6.89 (s, 1H), 4.59 (d, J = 16 Hz, 1H), 4.19 (d, J = 16 Hz, 1H), 4.15 (s, 1H), 0.32 (s, 9H).

(4R,9R)-5,10-dihydro-4,9-methanodithieno[3,2-b:3',2'-f][1,5]diazocine-2,7-dicarbaldehyde – TB-CHO

To solution of **TB** (100 mg, 0.43 mmol) in 6 mL of dry THF at 0 °C a solution of n-BuLi (0.8 mL, 1.6 M in hexane) was added and the mixture was stirred 30 min. at room temperature and then cooled to -78 °C. To the cooled solution N,N-dimethylformamide (255 mg, 1.5 eq., in 2 mL of dry THF) was added and the solution was warmed up to room temperature slowly and stirred for 30 min. at room temperature. Then, water was added to the reaction, extracted with dichloromethane (x3) and the organic phases were washed with brine and dried over MgSO₄. After removal of the solvent, the residue was purified by chromatography column in Hexane/Ethyl Acetate 1:2, to give the product **TB-CHO** as a yellowish solid (24mg, 18%).

¹H-NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃): δ (ppm) = 9.82 (s, 1H), 7.52 (s, 1H), 4.66 (d, J = 16 Hz, 1H), 4.28 (s, 1H), 4.23 (d, J = 16 Hz, 1H).

¹³C-NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃): δ (ppm) = 182.3, 146.5, 140.7, 134.3, 131, 67.6, 54.4.

2,2'-(((4R,9R)-5,10-dihydro-4,9-methanodithieno[3,2-b:3',2'-f][1,5]diazocine-2,7-diyl)bis(methanylylidene))dimalononitrile – TB1

To solution of **TB-CHO** (100 mg, 0.43 mmol) in a mixture of DCE/EtOH 1:1 at room temperature it was added 98 mg of **2** and 1 drop of piperidine and the reaction was stirred 30min. once the time is over, the reaction is washed with deionized water and extracted with chloroform. The organic phases were washed with brine and dried over MgSO₄. The obtained solid was purified by column chromatography (Silica gel flash, chloroform/methanol 90:1), obtaining 34 mg of **TB1** (53mg, 40%) as a yellow powder.

¹H-NMR (300 MHz, Acetone-*d*6): δ (ppm) = 8.32 (d, J = 0.6 Hz, 1H), 7.77 (d, J = 0.6 Hz, 1H), 4.80 (d, J = 18.0 Hz, 1H), 4.48 (d, J = 18.0, 1H), 4.37 (m, 1H).

¹³C-NMR (75 MHz, Acetone-*d*6): δ (ppm) = 152.71, 148.34, 137.98, 135.86, 133.53, 114.94, 114.21, 79.20, 77.24, 67.83, 55.20.

FTIR (ATR, CHCl₃): u (cm⁻¹): 2990, 2917, 2874, 2211, 1694, 1432, , 1235.

MALDI-HRMS (m/z): calculated for C₁₉H₁₀N₆S₂: 386.0408, found (M⁺): 386.0422.

2,2'-((5,5'-((4R,9R)-5,10-dihydro-4,9-methanodithieno[3,2-b:3',2'-f][1,5]diazocine-2,7-diyl)bis(thiophene-5,2-iy))bis(methanylylidene)) dimalononitrile – TB2

A solution of **TB-Sn** (65 mg, 0.011 mmol), **3** (61 mg, 0.025 mmol, 2.2 eq.) and Pd(Ph₃)₂Cl₂ (0.9 mg, 0.0011 mmol, 0.1 eq) in 10 mL of dry THF is stirred overnight at 85 °C. The reaction is cooled, the solvent volume is half-reduced and then 20 mL of hexane is added. The emerging solid was filtered and washed several times with hexane and methanol to obtain the pure product **TB2** as an orange solid (44 mg, 65%).

¹H-NMR (300 MHz, Acetone-*d*6): δ (ppm) = 8.37 (s, 1H), 7.88 (d, J = 4.1 Hz, 1H), 7.46 (s, 1H), 7.45 (d, J = 4.1 Hz, 1H), 4.64 (d, J = 17.1 Hz, 1H), 4.38 (d, J = 17.2 Hz, 1H), 4.30 (s, 1H).

¹³C-NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-*d*6): δ (ppm) = 152.40, 148.07, 146.91, 142.49, 133.27, 131.20, 127.00, 124.97, 123.90, 114.68, 113.96, 74.21, 53.12.

FTIR (ATR, CHCl₃): u (cm⁻¹): 2995, 2916, 2870, 2212, 1694, 1615, 1435, 1322, 1235.

MALDI-HRMS (m/z): calculated for C₂₇H₁₄N₆S₄: 550.0163, found (M⁺): 550.0170.

2,2'-((5',5'''-((4R,9R)-5,10-dihydro-4,9-methanodithieno[3,2-b:3',2'-f][1,5]diazocine-2,7-diyl)bis([2,2'-bithiophene]-5',5'-diyl))bis(methanylylidene)) dimalononitrile – TB3

A solution of **TB-Sn** (100 mg, 0.18 mmol), **4** (126 mg, 0.39 mmol, 2.2 eq.) and Pd(Ph₃)₂Cl₂ (12 mg, 0.02 mmol, 0.1 eq) in 10 mL of dry THF is stirred overnight at 85 °C. The reaction is cooled, the solvent volume is half-reduced and then 20 mL of hexane is added. The emerging solid is filtered and washed several times with hexane and methanol to obtain the pure product **TB3** as an orange solid (66 mg, 51%).

¹H-NMR (300 MHz, Acetone-*d*₆): δ (ppm) = 8.39 (s, 1H), 7.92 (d, J = 4.0 Hz, 1H), 7.58 (d, J = 4.0 Hz, 1H), 7.56 (d, J = 4.1 Hz, 1H), 7.27 (d, J = 4.0 Hz, 1H), 7.23 (s, 1H), 4.60 (d, J = 17.0 Hz, 1H), 4.34 – 4.25 (m, 2H).

¹³C-NMR (75 MHz, Acetone-*d*₆): δ (ppm) = 152.21, 148.69, 142.61, 141.03, 134.71, 134.36, 129.33, 125.77, 125.23, 124.14, 123.64, 122.22, 115.19, 114.57, 79.20, 76.28, 68.40, 54.01.

FTIR (ATR, CHCl₃): ν (cm⁻¹): 2995, 2917, 2875, 2210, 1694, 1615, 1432, 1375, 1312, 1235, 1175.

MALDI-HRMS (m/z): calculated for C₃₅H₁₈N₆S₆: 713.9917, found (M⁺⁺¹): 714.9997

Figure S1. ¹H-NMR spectrum of TB1 in Acetone-*d*₆.

Figure S2. ¹H-NMR spectrum of TB2 in Acetone-*d*₆.

Figure S3. ¹H-NMR spectrum of TB3 in Acetone-*d*₆.

Figure S4. COSY ^1H - ^1H -NMR spectrum of TB3 in Acetone- d_6 .

Figure S5. ^1H -NMR spectrum comparison of TB1, TB2 and TB3 in Acetone- d_6 .

Figure S6. ^{13}C -NMR spectrum of TB in CDCl_3 .

Figure S7. ^{13}C -NMR spectrum of TB1 in Acetone- d_6 .

Figure S8. ^{13}C -NMR spectrum of TB2 in DMSO- d_6 .

Figure S9. ^{13}C -NMR spectrum of TB3 in Acetone- d_6 .

Figure S10. IR spectrum of TB1.

Figure S11. IR spectrum of TB2.

Figure S12. IR spectrum of TB3.

Figure S13. MALDI-HRMS (m/z) spectrum of TB1.

Figure S14. MALDI-HRMS (m/z) spectrum of TB2.

Figure S15. MALDI-HRMS (m/z) spectrum of TB3.

2. Quantum Chemical Calculations

Computational Details

Ground and excited states geometries were optimized within the framework of the density functional theory (DFT) at the CAM-B3LYP/6-31g(d,p) level. Excitation energies and interstate spin-orbit coupling were computed using time-dependent DFT (TDDFT) at the CAM-B3LYP /6-311+g(d,p) level, with and without resorting to the Tamm-Dancoff approximation (TDA). Electron-hole correlation plots for the characterization of excited states were obtained using TheoDRE 3.0.⁵ All calculations were performed using Gaussian 16 and Q-Chem program packages.^{6, 7}

Structural characterization: ground state

Selected relevant geometrical parameters are defined in Figure S16 and reported for all compounds investigated in Table S1.

Figure S16. Definition of the geometrical parameters: $\theta_1 = \text{N1-C1-N2}$, $\theta_2 = \text{C2-N1-C3}$, $\theta_3 = \text{C4-C1-C5}$, θ_4 is defined as the angle between vectors S1-C4 and C5-S2, the twist of DCVT unit is evaluated by the dihedral angle $\theta_5 = \text{C2-C4-C6-C5}$, the deviation from planarity within the DCVT unit is characterized by the dihedral angle $\theta_6 = \text{S1-C7-C8-C9}$.

Table S1. Structural parameters at the ground state geometry.

	TB1	TB1-2H ⁺	TB2	TB3
θ_1	111.5	107.2	111.7	111.8
θ_2	113.4	113.5	113.2	113.2
θ_3	81.0	78.1	81.0	81.1
θ_4	78.1	81.3	77.8	78.3
θ_5	-24.5	-26.7	-24.8	-24.6
θ_6^a	-176.0	-173.8	-162.0	-157.7

^a θ_6 for **TB2** and **TB3** corresponds to the dihedral angle between the two first thiophene units of DCVT.

Conformers

Table S2. Relative energies (in kcal.mol⁻¹) of the cis and trans conformers of **TB1**, **TB2** and **TB3**.

(kcal.mol ⁻¹)	TB1	TB2	TB3
trans	0.43	0.00	0.00
cis	0.00	1.24	0.80

TDDFT data (ground state geometry)

Table S3. Vertical transition energies (in eV), oscillator strengths (in parentheses) and orbital contributions of monomers **DCVT1** and **DCVT2**, and molecules **TB1**, **TB2** and **TB3** calculated at the TDDFT level, and experimental values corresponding to the absorption maxima.

	state	exp	TDDFT	contributions
DCVT1	S ₁	/	3.99 (0.62)	98% H→L
TB1	S ₁	3.12	3.60 (0.90)	72% H→L + 25% H-1→L+1
	S ₂	/	3.73 (0.14)	56% H→L+1 + 40% H-1→L
	S ₃	3.83	4.09 (0.28)	66% H-2→L + 15% H-3→L+1 + 10% H-1→L+1 + 6% H→L
	S ₄	/	4.20 (0.10)	52% H-2→L+1 + 20% H-1→L + 17% H-3→L + 9% H→L+1
DCVT2	S ₁	/	3.32 (0.95)	96% H→L
TB2	S ₁	2.75	3.15 (1.65)	54% H→L + 38% H-1→L+1
	S ₂	/	3.30 (0.48)	49% H→L+1 + 44% H-1→L
TB3	S ₁	2.59	2.92 (2.08)	47% H→L + 38% H-1→L+1
	S ₂	/	3.03 (0.72)	44% H→L+1 + 42% H-1→L

Molecular orbitals at the ground state geometry

Figure S17. Molecular orbitals (HOMO-1, HOMO, LUMO and LUMO+1) involved in the excitations to the lowest singlet excited states of **TB1**, **TB2** and **TB3**.

Point dipole approximation

Exciton coupling for oblique arrangement of the transition dipoles can be evaluated using the point-dipole approximation (PDA) as:

$$V_{12}^{PDA} = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \left[\frac{\boldsymbol{\mu}_1 \cdot \boldsymbol{\mu}_2}{r_{12}^3} - 3 \frac{(\boldsymbol{\mu}_1 \cdot \mathbf{r}_{12})(\boldsymbol{\mu}_2 \cdot \mathbf{r}_{12})}{r_{12}^5} \right]$$

where \mathbf{r}_{12} is the vector distance between molecules 1 and 2, and $\boldsymbol{\mu}_1$ and $\boldsymbol{\mu}_2$ their respective transition dipole moments.

The following parameters have been used for the calculation:

Figure S18. Dipole-dipole interaction in **TB1** and associated parameters.

The Davydson splitting, i.e., the energy gap between the two lowest excited singlet states of the dimer, is then obtained as twice the exciton coupling of μ_1 and μ_2 and amounts to 0.045 eV.

e-h correlation plots (ground state geometry)

Figure S19. Electron-hole correlation plots for the S_1 state of (a) **TB1** considering DA as central fragment (without CC units of thiophene), (b) **TB1** considering only **TB**'s nitrogen atoms as central fragment, and of (c) the protonated **TB1**.

Figure S20. Electron-hole correlation plots for the S_1 state of **TB1**, **TB2** and **TB3** considering different fragmentation schemes: (left) defining the central fragment as the DA, without CC units of thiophene, (center) defining the central fragment as **TB** (DA + 2 thiophenes), (right) defining the side fragments as DCVT1.

Molecular orbitals at the relaxed S_1 geometry

Figure S23. Molecular orbitals (HOMO-1, HOMO, LUMO and LUMO+1) of **TB1**, **TB2** and **TB3** at their respective S_1 geometry.

TDDFT data (S_1 geometry)

Table S4. Vertical transition energies (in eV), oscillator strengths (in parentheses) and orbital contributions of **TB1**, **TB2** and **TB3** at their respective S_1 geometry calculated at the TDDFT level, and experimental values corresponding to the emission.

	exp	TDDFT	contributions
TB1	2.39	3.11 (0.42)	93% H→L
TB2	2.28	2.75 (1.33)	91% H→L
TB3	2.04	2.45 (1.79)	92% H→L

Table S5. TDDFT energy differences (ΔE in eV) between pairs of singlet and triplet states of monomer **DCVT2** and **TB2** evaluated at their respective relaxed S_1 geometry and associated spin-orbit coupling constants (SOC).

	TB2		DCVT2	
	$\Delta E(T_n-S_1)$	SOC (cm^{-1})	$\Delta E(T_n-S_1)$	SOC (cm^{-1})
T ₁	-1.79	0.3	-1.90	0.0
T ₂	-1.15	0.1	-0.34	0.0
T ₃	-0.30	0.2	0.58	0.3
T ₄	-0.01	0.6	0.84	0.3
T ₅	0.49	0.9	0.92	0.3
T ₆	0.76	0.9	1.21	0.4

e-h correlation plots (S_1 geometry)

Figure S24. Electron-hole correlation plots for the S_1 state of **TB1** (a), **TB2** (b) and **TB3** (c) at their respective relaxed S_1 geometries, considering DA as central fragment (without CC units of thiophene). Results for **TB3** were obtained at the CAM-B3LYP/6-311G(d,p) level.

Solvatochromic effects

Table S6. TDDFT energy differences (ΔE in eV), oscillator strength (f) and permanent dipole moment (DM in Debye) of the lowest excited singlet (S_1) of **TB1** at the ground (left) and excited (right) state geometries in toluene and THF computed at the CAM-B3LYP/6-31G(d,p) level. Ground state dipole moments in parenthesis.

solvent	S_0 geometry			S_1 geometry		
	ΔE	f	DM	ΔE	f	DM
toluene	3.41	1.12	10.01 (6.05)	2.92	0.59	12.95 (6.51)
THF	3.38	1.09	10.74 (6.55)	2.89	0.57	14.00 (7.45)

3. Transient electronic Absorption Spectroscopy

Qualitative comparison of triplet population

To obtain a concrete value for triplet absorptivity is a difficult task which involves the use of suitable triplet probes. These probes require complementary ground absorbance spectrum to our materials. In addition, their triplet absorbance spectra must appear in different places in the spectrum. These problems are further enhanced with materials with different absorbance spectra like the TBs, which would require to use different probe which would establish further error in the measurement.

Therefore, we did a simple qualitative comparison assuming that the TBs triplet relative absorptivity would be similar to their relative ground state absorptivity to obtain a superficial estimation. Assuming this, we obtained the following graph indicating the following trend in terms of triplet population **TB3>TB2>>>TB1**.

Figure S25. TA decays of the triplet population characterized by μ s-TAS. **TB2** and **TB3** solutions were excited at $100 \mu\text{J}/\text{cm}^2$ at 450 and 550 nm, respectively. Fittings have been added as dashed lines to help the eye.

Figure S26. Oxygen dependence experiments for (a) **TB2** and (b) **TB3**. TA decays were recorded under nitrogen (black), oxygen (red) and back to nitrogen (green). **TB2** and **TB3** solutions were excited at $100 \mu\text{J}/\text{cm}^2$ at 450 and 550 nm, respectively.

Figure S27. ps-TA decays of **TB1** solution probed at 750 nm excited at 415 nm at 0.5 mW (red) and 1 mW (black).

Figure S28. Pico-second transient absorption measurements for the three compounds under study carried out in: i) an apolar solvent as toluene and in a more polar solvent as THF. All at 298 K.

Figure S29. Global analysis decays obtained for (a) **TB1**, (b) **TB2** and (c) **TB3**. Fittings have been added as dashed lines to help the eye.

Figure S30. Relative population of triplet states for **TBn** materials using their ground state absorptivity and their μ s-TAS spectra.

Figure S31. Chemical structure of **DCVT2** as the monomer reference of **TB2**. This was prepared as the non-brominated version of compound **4** in Scheme 1.

Figure S32. Top: Excitation spectrum of **DCVT2** (black line) in CH₂Cl₂ at 298 K compared with its emission spectrum (red line). Bottom, left: pico-second transient absorption spectra of **DCVT2** in CH₂Cl₂ at 298 K. Bottom, right: time evolution of the absorbance of the excited states with different probes at the two ESA bands with the same excitation at 430 nm.

4. Quantum chemical calculations for the *trans* conformers

Table *trans* conformer. Vertical transition energies (in eV), oscillator strengths (in parentheses) and orbital contributions of *trans* TBn at their respective ground state geometry calculated at the TDDFT level, and experimental values corresponding to the absorption maxima.

	state	exp	TDDFT	contributions
TB1	S ₁	3.12	3.61 (0.62)	70% H→L + 27% H-1→L+1
<i>trans</i>	S ₂	/	3.73 (0.18)	53% H→L+1 + 40% H-1→L
TB2	S ₁	2.75	3.14 (1.48)	56% H→L + 36% H-1→L+1
<i>trans</i>	S ₂	/	3.29 (0.36)	50% H→L+1 + 43% H-1→L
TB3	S ₁	2.59	2.91 (1.85)	48% H→L + 39% H-1→L+1
<i>trans</i>	S ₂	/	3.02 (0.82)	45% H→L+1 + 42% H-1→L

Figure *trans* conformer. Molecular orbitals (HOMO-1, HOMO, LUMO and LUMO+1) involved in the excitations to the lowest singlet excited states of *trans* **TBn** at their respective ground state geometry.

Figure *trans* conformer. Electron-hole correlation plots for the S_1 state of *trans* **TBn** at their respective ground state (top) and relaxed excited state (bottom) geometries (considering DA as the central fragment, without CC units of thiophenes). Results for **TB3** at the S_1 geometry were obtained at the CAM-B3LYP/6-311G(d,p) level.

Table *trans* conformer. Vertical transition energies (in eV), oscillator strengths (in parentheses) and orbital contributions of *trans* **TBn** at their respective S_1 geometry calculated at the TDDFT level, and experimental values corresponding to the emission.

	exp	TDDFT	contributions
TB1	2.39	2.98 (0.27)	93% H→L
TB2	2.28	2.74 (1.19)	92% H→L
TB3	2.04	2.45 (1.65)	92% H→L

Figure *trans* conformer. Molecular orbitals (HOMO-1, HOMO, LUMO and LUMO+1) involved in the excitations to the lowest singlet excited states of *trans* TBn at their respective S_1 geometry.

Table *trans* conformer. TDDFT energy differences (ΔE in eV) between pairs of singlet triplet states of *trans* TBn together with the spin-orbit coupling constants (SOC), calculated at the relaxed S_1 geometry.

	TB1 <i>trans</i>		TB2 <i>trans</i>		TB3 <i>trans</i>	
	$\Delta E(T_n-S_1)$	SOC (cm ⁻¹)	$\Delta E(T_n-S_1)$	SOC (cm ⁻¹)	$\Delta E(T_n-S_1)$	SOC (cm ⁻¹)
T ₁	-1.64	2.7	-1.77	0.3	-1.66	0.2
T ₂	-1.03	0.5	-1.13	0.1	-0.93	0.1
T ₃	-0.37	1.7	-0.25	0.3	-0.49	0.0
T ₄	0.24	2.8	0.04	0.6	-0.13	0.1
T ₅	0.49	11.6	0.46	1.2	0.52	0.3
T ₆	0.76	0.5	0.76	1.3	0.72	0.6
T ₇	0.91	0.5	0.77	1.3	0.93	1.0
T ₈	1.06	11.7	0.89	0.6	1.01	0.7

Figure *trans* conformer. Electron/hole pair densities (orange/blue) for the S_1 and T_4 states of *trans* TB1 at the relaxed S_1 geometry.

Figure *trans* conformer. Electron/hole pair densities (orange/blue) for the S_1 and T_4 states of *trans* **TB2** and **TB3** at their respective relaxed S_1 geometries.

5. References

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